

THE SIGNIFICANT THEORETICAL RULES OF WORD STRESS IN UZBEK, KARAKALPAK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation:

The thesis is written to provide some theory about the word stress of the three languages(Uzbek, Karakalpak as well as English) comparing with each other and try to illustrate with examples.

Key words: stress, pitch, acoustic signs of a dynamic accent, the tension, the muscles of the speech organs, an accent, percussion, suprasegmental feature.

There is no doubt that core vocabularies which exist in every single language such as water, brother, apple, have stress on the first syllable in English language¹. For example:

Water: /'wɔ:tər/	Table: /'teɪbəl/	Father: /'fɑ:ðər/	Pretty: /'prɪti
Finger: /'fɪŋgər/	Ugly: /'ʌgli/	Butter: /'bʌtər/	Apple: /'æpəl/

However, general tendency is for the stressed syllable to be somewhere in the middle of the word, rather than on the first or last syllable in words of four, five, or six syllables. Additionally, certain suffixes determine on which of the other syllables the stress will fall. There are very many suffixes which cause the syllable before the suffix to be stressed. These are followings:

-ive (impressive)	iant (deviant)	-ial (substantial)	-ious (infectious)	-ical (economical)
-iate (deviate)	iary (pecuniary)	-ion (invention)	-ior (superior)	ible (impossible)
-ient (incipient)	-iable (negotiable)	-ish (diminish)	ian (median)	-ity (opportunity)

¹ Celce-MurciaM., Brinton D., Goodwin J. Teaching Pronunciation: A Reference 8. for Teachers of English to Speakers of Other Languages. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1996.

-ium (premium)	-ify (identify)	-ic (geographic)	-iar (familiar)	-io (radio)
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It doesn't matter if the stress was on a different syllable in the form of the word without the suffix (sometimes called the 'base' word); the stress will move from wherever it was to the syllable before the suffix when any of these suffixes are added² in English language.

Though, In Uzbek language, word stress is more predictable and is usually placed on the second syllable from the end (penultimate syllable) in multisyllabic words. In addition to that Unlike English, which has variable stress patterns, Uzbek generally follows a regular stress pattern that can be predicted based on the word's structure. This makes it easier to determine stress in Uzbek words. If a word has fewer syllables, stress typically falls on the initial syllable. However, in longer words, the penultimate syllable still receives primary stress³. Loanwords in Uzbek often retain their original stress patterns, which may differ from the general Uzbek stress rules. These loanwords may maintain the stress pattern of the language they originated from. Uzbek word: **"O'zbekiston" (Uzbekistan) Word stress: o'ZBEKiston**, The stress falls on the penultimate syllable, which is typical in Uzbek.

Uzbek word: **"kitob" (book),**

Word stress: KItob Again, the stress falls on the penultimate syllable. **"Savol"- "saVOL" (Question), "Bolalar" "boLalar" (Children), "O'quvchi"- "o'QUVchi" (Student); "Darslik" (Textbook) "darsLIK"** the stress falls on the second-to-last syllable.

If we compare the word stress of Karakalpak language, stress typically falls on the first syllable of words. However, there can be exceptions depending on specific words and their phonetic structure. It is important to note that these examples provide a general understanding of word stress in Karakalpak, and there may be variations in different dialects or individual words⁴.

"Bala"- "BAla", (Child) **"Ýashik"- "ÝA-shik."** (Box) - The stress falls on the first syllable.

² Anne C. ERRORS OF STRESS AND INTONATION. Laboratory of Experimental Psychology. University of Sussex. Brighton, England. 1980.

³ Abduazizov A. Theoretical Phonetics Of Modern English-Tashkent.: "Укитувчи", 1986. 9. Abulazova

⁴ A. Dawletov "Til bilimi". –Nukus, 2017. B.74

As we can see above, the word stress of three language Karakalpak, Uzbek and English have some similar peculiarities comparing with each other such as some words in three languages have stress on the first syllable.

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